

A study of the removal of dyes by Goda sand

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Adsorption of dyes on Goda sand was investigated to assess the possibility of treating waste-water streams from dye works for removal of toxic materials. The effect of several factors governing the adsorption such as initial concentration, temperature, pH have been studied. The adsorption equilibrium is well co-related by Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherms.

A large quantity of dyes is discharged into waste streams by the textile industries. Now-a-days, thermally stable dyes are introduced, which are difficult to degradation after use. Many colour effluents are composed of non-biologically oxidizable organic compounds. These can be separated by adsorption method.

The discharge of dye into natural stream has created significant concern as the dye imparts toxicity and impedes light penetration and this upsets the biological activity. Among physico-chemical treatment processes, adsorption is found to be highly effective, cheap and an easy method. Many workers investigated adsorption of dyes on different adsorbent such as acetyl trimethyl-ammonium bromide treated silica¹, silica² activated carbon obtained from dust of leather industry³. Some of the workers reported adsorption of chemically and biologically important compounds on to solid surfaces^{4-6,8}.

Research survey reveals that various adsorbents are used to remove dye-stuff from the waste water such as wood, fire clay, etc. Khattri and Singh⁷ reported the removal of basic dyes from aqueous solution using sand collected from the Sone river (U.P.). For the present work, we have selected Goda sand collected from Godavari river, Paithan (Maharashtra) as adsorbent.

Result and discussion

Adsorption isotherms :

The fraction removal of dye (F_R) was calculated using equation

$$F_R = \frac{(C_0 - C)}{C_0} \quad (1)$$

Langmuir adsorption isotherm model was applied for

adsorption equilibrium

$$\frac{C_e}{Q_c} = \frac{1}{Q_0 b} + \frac{C_e}{Q_c} \quad (2)$$

where C_e is concentration of dye in ppm after equilibrium, Q_c is the amount of dye in ppm adsorbed per g of adsorbent after equilibrium, Q_0 and b are Langmuir constant related to adsorption capacity and energy of adsorption respectively.

The linear plot of C_e/Q_c vs C_e shows that the adsorption obeys Langmuir model. Values of Q_0 and b are presented in Table 5.

The essential characteristics of Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless constant, separation factor or equilibrium parameter R_L which is given as

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + bC_0} \quad (3)$$

where C_0 is initial concentration in ppm and b is Langmuir constant.

The R_L values between zero and one indicate favorable adsorption.

R_L values	Type of isotherm
$R_L > 1$	Unfavorable
$R_L = 1$	Linear
$0 < R_L < 1$	Favorable
$R_L = 0$	Irreversible

Khatri⁷ reported adsorption of dyes on sone sand and the value of R_L from 0.07 to 0.12 for methylene blue

where as for malachite green varies from 0.08 to 0.13. However for the adsorption of Cr ion on activated carbon, Bandhopadhy⁹ reported $R_L = 0.59$. De and Basu¹⁰ studied adsorption of methylene blue on modified saw dust and they reported the value of $R_L = 0.025$.

The Freundlich adsorption isotherm was also applied

$$\log \left(\frac{x}{m} \right) = \log k + \frac{1}{n} \log C_e \quad (4)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of dye and x/m is the amount adsorbed.

The plot of $\log (x/m)$ vs $\log C_e$ was obtained to be linear. This shows that the adsorption follows Freundlich isotherm. The values of n obtained were between 2 and 10 which indicates favorable adsorption.

In the present work the adsorption kinetics was studied by using Lagergren equation

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{K'_{ad}t}{2.303} \quad (5)$$

where q is the amount adsorbed at time t and q_e is the amount adsorbed at equilibrium time.

Linear plots of $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t indicate the applicability of Lagergren equation. Further, it confirmed the first order kinetics for adsorption process. The values of K'_{ad} are shown in Table 5.

The rate constant of intra-particle diffusion K_p were determined using Weber and Moris relationship by plotting amount of dye adsorbed versus square root of time.

$$q = K_p t^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

The results reveal that the initial part of these plots is straight lines, which do not pass through the origin, showing that the intra-particle diffusion is not the only rate controlling step.

Sand samples are generally rich in metal oxides. Khattri and Singh suggest that when these oxides are mixed with the dye solution, undergo surface hydroxylation which give negatively charged surface. The surface complex is formed at the adsorbate-adsorbent interface owing to the interaction of the negatively charged surface and dye cation.

The normalized root mean square error (NRMS) for both the isotherm was calculated using eqn. (7),

$$NRMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum \left[\frac{Y_{e',exp} - Y_{e',cal}}{Y_{e',exp}} \right]^2} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

where $Y_{e'}$ is calculated for Langmuir isotherm using eqn. (8).

$$Y_{e'} = \frac{(K_1 Q C_e)}{1 + K_1 C_e} \quad (8)$$

where as for Freundlich isotherm $Y_{e'}$ is calculated using eqn. (9).

$$Y_{e'} = K_2 C_e^b \quad (9)$$

$$\ln Y_{e'} = \ln K_2 + \frac{1}{n} \ln C_e \quad (10)$$

NRMS error obtained for the present investigation is given in Table 5.

Effect of contact time :

In adsorption studies, effect of contact time plays vital role irrespective of the other experimental parameters affecting adsorption kinetics. The adsorption studies were carried out at different contact time at constant initial concentration of dye with a fixed dose of adsorption. The data (Table 1) reveals that initially, adsorption is rapid and becomes slow and stagnates with increase in time. The exponential adsorption indicates first-order kinetics nature of adsorbate-adsorbent system.

Table 1. Variation of contact time

Temp. = 27 ± 0.5°, initial conc. = 50 ppm				
Contact time (min)	% Adsorption of Methylene blue	% Adsorption of Malachite green	Fraction removal of Methylene blue	Fraction of Malachite green
		F_R	F_R	
5	30	25	0.30	0.25
10	38	32	0.38	0.32
15	52	45	0.52	0.45
20	60	62	0.60	0.62
25	75	67	0.75	0.67
30	83	73	0.83	0.73
35	85	78	0.85	0.78
60	86	80	0.86	0.80
120	88	81	0.88	0.81

Effect of initial concentration :

The effect of initial concentration of dye solution on the amount of dye adsorbed on the Goda sand was studied with a fixed dose of adsorbent and constant contact time by varying the initial concentration of dye. The data is presented in Table 2. It reveals that the amount of dye adsorbed exponentially increases while the percentage removal decreases with the increase in initial concentra-

Table 2. Variation of initial concentration

Concn. of solution C_o (ppm)	Methylene blue		Malachite green	
	Amount adsorbed Q_e (ppm)	Equilibrium concentration $C_e = C_o - Q_e$ (ppm)	Amount adsorbed Q_e (ppm)	Equilibrium concentration $C_e = C_o - Q_e$ (ppm)
50	44	6	39	11
100	85	15	74	26
150	123	27	108	42
200	162	38	139	61
250	197	53	172	68
300	219	81	194	106

tion of dye. This might be due to the lack of available active sites on the adsorbent surface compared to the relatively large number of active sites required for the high initial concentration of dye.

Table 3. Variation of adsorbent

Initial concn. = 300 ppm		
Weight of adsorbent (g)	Amount of Methylene blue adsorbed Q_e (ppm)	Amount of Malachite green adsorbed Q_e (ppm)
1	88	79
2	152	143
3	207	177
4	243	223
5	258	244

Variation of adsorbent :

The variation of adsorbent is studied at fixed dose of adsorbate i.e. with a constant initial concentration of dye with optimum contact time. The adsorption increases exponentially with increasing amount of adsorbent. This might be due to increase in availability of the active sites due to the increase in the surface area.

Effect of pH :

As the adsorbent surface is negatively charged in pres-

Table 4. Variation of pH

Initial concn. = 100 ppm		
pH	Amount of Methylene blue adsorbed	Amount of Malachite green adsorbed
3.10	52	57
4.04	55	62
5.13	59	66
5.97	64	69
6.93	67	71

Table 5. Adsorption parameters/constants

		Methylene blue	Malachite green
Langmuir constants	Q_o mg/g	340.47	388.04
	b L/mg	0.023	0.010
Freundlich constants	R_L	0.126	0.260
	K	3.43	2.96
Rate constants	N	3.28	2.91
	K'_{ad}	0.00717	0.04180
NRM values	K_p	0.2397	0.2737
	Freundlich method	4.57%	1.70%
	Langmuir method	9.73%	6.13%

ence of OH^- the increasing electrostatic attraction between positive adsorbate (dye^{2+}) species and negative adsorbent particles (Goda sand) would lead to increased adsorption of the dyes.

This study was carried out with dye solution of 100 ppm in the range of 3.0 to 7.0. Hence, increase in the pH of solution from 3.0 to 7.0 adsorption of dyes increases. The rapid uptake of dye at higher pH indicates that the process could be ion exchange in nature where the positive dye molecules bind with negatively charged adsorbents. Lower pH is unfavorable for adsorption. This is due to excess of hydrogen ion and binding of dye molecule on sorption site.

Experimental

All the solutions were prepared by using doubly distilled water. Dyes i.e. Methylene blue and Malachite green were used for the present study. Goda sand samples were collected from Godavari river at Paithan, Dist. Aurangabad (Maharashtra). The samples were sieved for particles of 16-mesh size, then boiled with concentrated HCl to remove surface impurities, and washed with boiling water repeatedly till the complete removal of chloride ions. The sample was dried, activated at 400° for four hours and then allowed to cool.

Batch adsorption experiments were carried out by shaking fixed quantity of dye solution with known concentration containing 1 g of treated Goda sand for about two hours. The remaining amount of dye was estimated in the supernatant solutions spectrophotometrically. For kinetic measurement, different aliquots were withdrawn at regular time intervals. The effects of different parameters on the adsorption of dyes using the sand were investigated.

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